

APPLICATION OF WHATSAPP VOICE NOTE BASED COOPERATIVE LEARNING ON STUDENT COMMUNICATION SKILLS

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Abstract

This research is motivated by the low communication skills of students in Javanese language subjects, especially in class XII students of SMKN 3 Malang. This research was conducted to determine the effect of the Whatsapp Voice Note-based cooperative learning method on online learning on students' communication skills in Javanese. This study uses a pre-experimental method. The subjects consisted of 35 students. Communication skills were measured by written tests (pretest and posttest) and observation sheets. Communication skills tests and observation sheets were prepared and developed based on 21st-century communication indicators. Analysis of written test data (pretest and posttest) in this study were analyzed using statistical tests using the Statistics Package for Social Science (SPSS) software and performed manually using Microsoft Excel 2010. The observation sheet data were analyzed using the percentage calculation results. The data obtained from the study revealed that the application of the Whatsapp Voice Note-based cooperative learning method affected communication skills. This finding might be considered by Javanese language teachers to improve their communication skills.

Keywords: Student Communication Skill, Whatsapp Voice Note, Cooperative Learning

1. Introduction

In the 21st century, Indonesia received a golden generation in its golden age. The world of work in the 21st century is in a more international, multicultural, and interconnected position (Scott, 2015). The characteristics of 21st Century Learning are the development of learning activities that can lead students to achieve Higher Level Thinking Skills (HOTS), familiarize students with reading and writing activities through the School Literacy Movement (GLS), the selection of learning methods that can emphasize students. Centralized Learning (SCL). All of these things are expected to be integrated with learning activities (Sujana, 2020).

Some economists believe that education can solve the problems of poverty, low productivity, and slow economic growth in a country. The welfare of a community can be achieved by increasing the level of education as a process of building skills which in turn can increase income. An educated society is considered the key to achieving prosperity. On the other hand, the people themselves believe that education is a way out to get a better job with a better wage rate besides being able to increase one's degree (Suherti, 2006).

The world of work demands a change in competencies so that the ability to think critically, solve problems, and collaborate becomes important competencies in

learning in the 21st century. Verbal and written communication skills contribute to career development in the 21st century. However, the results of research conducted by Rusman stated that so far the orientation of existing educational institutions seems to be still directed at how graduates can fill existing job formations, and not many educational institutions have revealed how education can foster new knowledge in new ones. profession. and fostering a new attitude of life (Rusman, 2014). Apart from the above orientation, according to Mulyasa, other factors that cause the low quality of teaching include learning resources that have not been fully utilized by both teachers and students (Mulyasa, 2009).

The main focus of educators should be to develop important competencies according to the needs needed in the 21st century, one of which is communication skills, this is because currently, we are in the middle of the 21st century, inevitably students must have the skills needed in the era of the 21st century. 21. One way to improve student communication skills is to use cooperative-based learning methods. Cooperative learning is a form of learning that can improve learning systems that have weaknesses. Cooperative learning is a learning strategy that can improve student learning achievement and foster social relationships, foster acceptance of deficiencies in themselves and others, and make students aware of students' needs to learn to think about problem-solving, and integrate knowledge with skills (Trianto, 2007). This is supported by several studies that prove that cooperative learning can improve student academic achievement and social attitudes through collaboration between students and building student social skills (Fogarty and McTighe, 1993).

In the era of the Covid-19 pandemic, one of the most widely used media is WhatsApp. The use of WhatsApp Groups as a learning medium occurs at the elementary school level. Of course, due to various considerations. At the higher education level, WhatsApp is only one of the media. Unlike elementary schools, from a survey conducted by researchers, 100% of online learning only uses WhatsApp group media (reporter tempo, 2020). The WhatsApp voice note-based cooperative learning method in this study is the steps in the learning process designed in such a way that students are directly involved in the preparation, implementation, and follow-up of the voice note-based learning method. Cooperative learning used in this research is cooperative learning type STAD with stages that include preparation, teaching, team learning, testing, and team reflection.

Based on the description above, the researcher took the research title "*Application of Cooperative Learning-Based Whatsapp Voice Notes in Student Communication Skills*". This research is important to do to see the extent to which students' communication skills through the application of cooperative learning methods based on WhatsApp voice notes.

2. Literature Review

2.1. STAD Cooperative Based Learning

The new paradigm of education places more emphasis on developing the learning potential of students. All students must be active in seeking and developing knowledge. The truth of knowledge is not limited to what is conveyed by the teacher. The teacher must be a facilitator who guides students to form knowledge independently. It is hoped that through this new educational paradigm students are

active in learning and discussing in class, dare to convey ideas, accept other people's ideas and have high self-confidence Zamroni in (Hadi, 2005). The one-way learning process eliminates students' courage to express opinions. Students tend not to know the teacher's mistakes. Students become more individualistic. Students do not care about their peers who do not understand the material because according to them the teacher is in charge of providing understanding to students about learning material.

The learning model that is suitable for increasing student social interaction and student achievement is by applying the cooperative learning model. The application of cooperative learning will make it easier for students to find and understand difficult concepts if students can discuss the problems they face with their friends. This is supported by research from Slavin which states that cooperative learning can improve student achievement and can realize student needs in learning social interaction (Slavin, 2010).

One of the cooperative learning models that can be applied is the STAD cooperative learning model. STAD cooperative learning model is a learning model that involves students taking an active role in the form of small groups so that students can interact with each other in solving a problem (Fitriana, 2013). Meanwhile, according to (Prabowo, 2015), STAD is a cooperative learning model that is easy to apply in learning because of the simplicity of the steps.

2.2. WhatsApp Voice Note

Cetinkaya states that there are so many instant messaging applications that can operate on mobile devices, it seems that the WhatsApp application is one of the most preferred mobile-based applications (Cetinkaya, 2017). Referring to Cetinkaya that technology is currently important and effective in language learning. According to (La Hanisi, A., Risdiany, R., Dwi Utami, Y., & Sulisworo, 2018) define that WhatsApp is a web and smartphone-based instant messaging application that allows users to exchange information using various media, including text messages, images, videos, and audio.

Mobile assisted language learning (MALL) is one of the most discussed topics. Using mobile devices to learn a language may be effective because mobile devices are such a large part of our social life today (Salamat, A., & Pourgharib, 2017). According to (Kukulaska-Hulme, Agnes and Shield, 2008), defines MALL as "the use of technology such as cell phones, MP3 / MP4 players, and palmtop computers for language learning." They also argue that mobile learning is a type of learning that occurs with the help of devices. cellular. This means that mobile learning is a tool that will help us learn to use mobile devices.

The media that teachers can apply in learning communication skills is WhatsApp. WhatsApp is a tool for communicating with other people via instant messages. People using WhatsApp can send all kinds of information such as text messages, documents, videos, audio, and pictures. On WhatsApp, several features can help teachers and students in the teaching and learning process. They record voice, video, and voice calls. Thus, WhatsApp can be applied to the cell phone.

3. Research Methods

The research method used is the pre-experimental method. The subjects in this study were classes in Vocational High Schools in Malang City for the 2019/2020

Academic Year, totaling 35 students. The sampling technique was carried out by purposive sampling. Measurement of the influence of nonverbal communication skills was carried out through pretest and posttest so that the empirical design was "The One group Pretest-Posttest Desing" (Fraenkel and Wallen, 2012).

The instrument used to measure the effect of non-verbal communication skills was a description test consisting of 10 questions. Meanwhile, verbal communication skills were measured by the observation sheet and verbal communication skills rubric. The instrument for measuring students' verbal communication skills uses statements that measure verbal communication skills with an assessment rubric. The data in this study used Microsoft Excel 2010 and SPSS support programs.

4. Result and Discussion

4.1. Pre-class, In class, and after class activities

Pre Classes are neatly arranged in the form of a WhatsApp group. The teacher distributes material to be delivered tomorrow along with some guides that students can read before class starts. Students get instructions to read the material in advance while waiting for class hours scheduled by the school. Students are also divided into several groups, each group is then divided into several job descriptions that can be selected. Students are free to choose what they will serve. These could be librarians (data search team), editors (grammar revision team), designers (PowerPoint mixing team for presentations), and chairperson (person in charge and person in charge of group work). This is after I learned that online-based study guides are very important in their function. Students who are not provided with proper guidance will usually be confused in the online era because of limited face-to-face meetings with teachers.

The next stage is activities carried out in class, in the first 5 minutes the teacher directs students to fill out online attendance available on the google form that the teacher has made and the link is attached to the WhatsApp group description. After that, the teacher continues to explain the material according to the material sheets that have been distributed at the pre-class stage. The time allocated for this activity is 15 minutes, the material presented by the teacher is the Text of the Research Report "Literature Review". In the next 15 minutes, the teacher invites students to discuss and ask questions about things that have not been understood.

After that, in the next 45 minutes, the teacher proposed several themes. Students are directed to choose the preferred theme. The teacher then gives examples of how to work under the job descriptions that have been divided into pre-class classes. The teacher gives examples of how to be a good librarian, be a good editor, be a good designer, and how to be a good presenter. At the end of the lesson, the teacher selects one member of the group to provide a conclusion about the day's material. The teacher does not forget to choose the group that will present the next presentation according to the chosen theme.

In the next learning process, students make presentations in turns at each learning hour, students collect assignments according to what they do. Students who feel that they are librarians submit assignments to the librarian section, students who become moderators submit assignments to that section as moderators. At the end of a theme that ranges from 4 to 5 teacher meetings, add up the number of points from all groups, and announce the best group.

4.1. Student ability to non-verbal communication

.The staistic students to non-verbal communication (pre-test), after (post-test), and N-gain during application of whatsapp voice note based cooperative learning methods can be seen in table 1.

Table 1. Data statistic student non-verbal communication skills

Statistics	Value		N-gain
	Pretest	Postesst	
Average	15.79	31.29	0.55
Variance	9.68	18.64	0.02
At least	10	21	0.19
Maximum	21	39	0.83
Standard deviation	3.11	4.32	0.15
Median	15	32	0.58

Table1 shows that there is a difference between the pretest and posttest. The difference between pretest and posttest value can be seen from the N-gain value that indicates there is impact on non-verbal communication skills of students after implementation whatsapp voice note based cooperative learning method. As for the N-gain values are included into the category of **medium**.

4.2. Student ability to verbal communication

Table 2 shows the result of the observation sheet and communication verbal skills rubrics.

Table 2. Students ability to verbal communication

Aspects observed	Score	Category
Clarity, speed, volume, and articulation can be accepted for the purpose of communication	70%	Medium
Communication can be understood with a few minor flaws.	76%	Good
Quiet behavior showed	77%	Good
Responsive during the presentation process	75%	Medium
Trying response to cues audience	70%	Medium

Data about students ability to verbal communication showed on table 2, that most students did not know much about clarity, speed, volume, and articulation can be accepted for the purpose of communication. and trying response to cues audience. Students did not know much about the meaning and the importance of clarity, speed, volume, and articulation can be accepted for the purpose of communication. and trying response to cues audience. But, some students had better.

4.3. Disccusion

Based on the results of the study, there are several improvements in communication skills which indicate that the application of the WhatsApp-based cooperative learning model affects students' communication skills. The amount of influence on WhatsApp-based cooperative learning can be seen from the descriptive analysis. The results of the descriptive analysis show that the value of students' communication skills is at a good level. Thus, it can be concluded that

learning with the WhatsApp-based cooperative learning model affects students' communication skills.

The findings in this study indicate that the WhatsApp-based cooperative learning model has a positive effect on students' communication skills with the tendency for most students to get moderate grades due to several factors. The first factor is the influence of the cooperative learning model itself. The cooperative learning model is a method or step used in the learning process by inviting students to be actively involved in answering a problem or theme given to them. The stages of the STAD cooperative learning model: (1) Delivering goals and motivating students; (2) Presenting information; (3) Organizing students into study groups; (4) Guiding group work and study; (5) Evaluation; and (6) giving (Novriansyah, 2013). From the six steps, it is hoped that the teacher will not only be able to convey learning material but also be able to provoke students to answer the problems posed in a fun way. Furthermore, the addition of the WhatsApp-based learning model into the cooperative learning model makes the learning model more attractive and complete.

The second factor is student activity. By playing a clear division of tasks and job descriptions, students become more enthusiastic in participating in learning, so that the delivery of communication skills that is expected can be adjusted to the teaching material so that it is accepted happily and is not tense. Learning with cooperative methods can also guide students' thinking about the importance of cooperation and collaboration in life, the learning process is carried out to position students to be direct observers of presentations made by friends, and students who act as presenters can feel how to collaborate. to achieve exposure that others can accept. Unlike the case with conventional learning models which make students listen more to lectures, so students tend to be passive. In this type of learning the teacher usually dominates learning activities.

In learning conducted by lecturing, students tend to feel tense and find it difficult to understand the lessons delivered. Students become accustomed to listening, not used to expressing their opinions. Learning with the WhatsApp-based cooperative learning model provides students with direct experience of how to work together in a team, how to search for data, and how to convey the results of group work that has been done so that they can be accepted by others designed to be more fun. Thus, students' communication skills can be better honed. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by (Handayani, 2014) which states that the Procedure Text Speaking Learning Model through STAD type cooperative learning meets the effective criteria shown by student activity in learning, student responses, and student achievement. competence both individually. nor classic. Furthermore (Nurazizah, 2019) WhatsApp Voice note is an interesting learning activity, positive activity, and WhatsApp voice notes are easy to use. Finally, this study suggests other researchers involve objective data, enrich instrumentation, add research samples, and use other methods and designs to enrich the data. Therefore, the results of this study have succeeded in strengthening research related to WhatsApp-based cooperative learning models to improve communication skills.

5. Conclusions and suggestions

Based on the research conducted on the pretest and posttest scores, it can be seen from the N-gain value indicates that there is an influence on students' non-

verbal communication skills after the application of the noted voice note-based cooperative learning method. Meanwhile, the N-gain value is included in the medium category.

Based on these conclusions, several things can be stated: (1) the researcher must know the characteristics and abilities of each student so that the distribution of the group is evenly distributed and learning activities can be carried out properly, (2) the researcher can calculate the time at each stage of learning to make it more efficient because time is one of the obstacles in the learning process in the Covid era, (3) all educators, especially Javanese language teachers, can consider WhatsApp-based cooperative learning as an alternative to improve student communication skills.

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